

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a ship found at Køge Harbour, KNV804, Denmark.

Aoife Daly, Ph.D..

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In the summer of 2018, remains of a ship were found during excavations, carried out by Museum Sydøstdanmark, at Køge Harbour, Denmark. An extensive dendrochronological analysis was planned, and samples have been gradually sawn from selected timbers as the documentation of each timber element from the ship was completed. A selection of trenails and diverse other wooden pieces were also selected for wood genus identification. This report presents the full results of this analysis.

(Samples from a small selection of barrel staves and heads were also sampled, but these are reported separately.)

In all 83 samples were taken for dendrochronological analysis, but three of these had too few rings and these were only analysed to identify wood genus. Samples are from framing timbers, keel and riders and from hull planks and an outer extra plank layer, forward on the hull. The results are organised and described according to these structural groups.

Frames

A total of 34 frames have been analysed. Of these 29 are dated (fig. 1). The shapes of two of the frames (x153 & x 154) lead to the suggestion that these frames are fashioned from re-used keel timbers (Jeppe Færch-Jensen pers comm). These two are dated. The sample from one of these, x154, has sapwood preserved. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that this re-used keel was made from is placed at c. AD 1496-1526.

There is a homogenous group formed by the majority of the dated frames, marked with orange in fig. 1. Of these 21 have sapwood preserved, and of these 10 have complete sapwood to bark edge. The felling dates for the samples with bark edge are winter AD 1523-24, spring/summer AD 1525, winter AD 1526-27 and spring/summer AD 1526. The estimated felling dates for the majority of the other samples in this group fall within this timespan. We can therefore conclude that the frames for the original building phase of the ship (apart from the evident re-use of two keels) are from oaks felled over a few years, chiefly from spring/summer AD 1525 to winter AD 1526-27.

A frame fragment (x172) is also dated. It has complete sapwood to bark edge preserved. It is from a tree felled a little later, in winter AD 1528-29. Another frame (x166), also with complete sapwood to bark edge preserved, is from a tree felled winter AD 1546-47. This frame might belong to the later modification to the hull (discussed below). It was not actually attached to the ship when it was excavated, so it does not have a firm contextual position (Jeppe Færch-Jensen pers comm).

Fig. 1. Køge ship, Denmark. Diagram showing the chronological position of the tree-ring curves from the dated timbers.

One frame (x117) was analysed very early in the excavation, through coring. When coring waterlogged wood, the soft outer rings generally do not remain intact, so only heartwood is preserved on this sample. The tree-ring curve from another sample, from the same frame, this time sawn from the timber, had the complete sapwood to bark preserved, allowing the precise felling year for the tree that this frame was made from, at spring/summer AD 1526.

Stem

One sample was taken from a ship's stem. It has complete sapwood to bark edge preserved and is from a tree felled in spring/summer AD 1524. This dating fits with the dates of the main group of frames.

Planks

A total of 39 oak hull planks from the ship are analysed. These can be divided into a main group from the single shell hull and an added extra sheathing outermost, at the prow of the vessel.

The single shell planks

Thirty-two samples were taken from hull planks belonging to the main single layer clinker planking. These planks are a mixture of radially converted (fig. 2) and tangentially converted (fig. 3) planks. Nine of these have only heartwood preserved while sapwood is observed on the remaining 23 planks samples.

None of the samples from the main hull planks have bark edge preserved but some (x275 & x290) have possible bark edge. These are from trees possibly felled AD 1523 and AD 1524 respectively. This dating agrees neatly with the datings for the frames described above.

The double plank layer

Seven samples are from the extra plank layer. Although I have designated them as either radial or tangential, they are very particularly wedge shaped, as an example shows in fig. 4. All seven samples are dated. Three have sapwood preserved but none have bark edge. Allowing for missing sapwood, the trees that this group of planks were made from were felled c. AD 1538-1550 (see fig. 1).

Riders

Samples from three riders were analysed and these are all dated. Two have sapwood to bark edge preserved. One, x6, is from a tree felled in winter AD 1538-39, while the other, x10, is from spring/summer 1539.

The undated samples

Of the samples analysed dendrochronologically, seven could not be dated (see catalogue). Four are from frames, containing 75, 56, 75 and 43 rings respectively. One sample is from the keel. This contained just 55 rings. Finally, two samples are from ceiling planks. These contain 56 and 57 tree-rings respectively.

All in all, it is clear from the results of the dendrochronological analysis that the original building phase of the ship was completed probably during winter 1526-27, of timber felled over a couple of years (marked with a vertical red line in fig. 1). Major modifications to the prow of the vessel, with the addition of an extra plank layer and supported by riders inboard, took place perhaps in spring/summer 1539 (marked with a vertical dark-blue line in fig. 1). One framing timber gives a later felling date, of winter AD 1546-47, but this frame was not found in a firm context.

Twelve of the barrel parts found in and around the wreck, that will be reported separately, are dated. These finds were not from articulated barrels so they do not represent the ship's cargo as such, but rather are random barrel parts that might have been used as dunnage, or they were just waste. There is however also the danger that these were not at all associated with the ship, if they had randomly drifted into the site in the ebb and flow of a busy harbour. The youngest is a barrel stave dating to after AD 1556. If these barrel parts belong to activity during the ship's usage, they indicate that the ship might have been around 30 years old when it was abandoned at Køge harbour.

Fig. 2. Køge ship, Denmark. The cross section of sample x210, a radially converted plank from the single plank layer (photo Aoife Daly).

Fig. 3. Køge ship, Denmark. The cross section of sample x455, a tangentially converted plank from the single plank layer (photo Aoife Daly).

Fig. 4. Køge ship, Denmark. The cross section of sample x320, from the double plank layer (photo Aoife Daly).

Provenance

The correlation between each sample with each other indicates two major groups (table 1) clearly dividing the frames and the planks.

The majority of the frames group together, in terms of their correlation (highlighted with orange). An average of 24 tree-ring curves from the frames is calculated (Z2261M02). It is 153 years in length and covers the period AD 1374-1526.

The plank group can be further sub-divided, however. A very strongly correlating group is highlighted with pink. These are so similar, these 13 could have been fashioned from a single tree, or trees growing close to each other. The group is a mixture of tangential and radial converted planks. Another sub-group is highlighted with blue. These seven strongly correlating tree-ring curves are all from the double plank layer. The rest of this large second group (highlighted with green in table 1) is quite homogeneous, suggesting that the supply of timber for the planks for the ship came from the same geographical area/forest. Three averages are made from the plank group. The pink group that might all be from one tree (Z226ST01) is 308 years in length, covering the period AD 1216-1523. The double plank group (blue) forms an average (Z2261M03) of 274 years covering AD 1264-1537. The green group, which includes the rest of the planks, except one (x455 marked in dark-green) are averaged to a mean curve (Z2261M01) 425 years long, covering AD 1098-1522.

Filenames	-	-	Z2261M02 frames	Z226M007	
-	Start	dates	AD1374	AD1371	
-	Dates	end	AD1526	AD1488	
TWWFMD01	AD1216	AD1660	6.41	4.42	NL Twente/Westfalen 51 trees (Dominguez Delmas unpubl)
BASPARH	AD279	AD1994	6.22	-	Paris Basin (Bernard pers comm)
nlzuidmm	AD427	AD1752	6.06	3.25	South Netherlands (Jansma pers comm)
G3313Z01	AD1354	AD1526	6.04	-	Hameln 8 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G311TZ01	AD1433	AD1580	6.00	-	Einbeck 11 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G330KZ01	AD1373	AD1535	5.84	3.38	Bückeberg 8 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
DM200005	AD915	AD1873	5.48	3.99	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni)
G340ZZ01	AD1365	AD1546	5.32	-	BMU 20 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
nlmidden	AD1023	AD1666	5.29	3.30	Mid Netherlands (Jansma pers comm)
G350ZZ01	AD1401	AD1574	5.27	-	Lüneburg 17 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
DM200006	AD914	AD1873	5.22	3.35	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)
G311NZ02	AD1435	AD1553	5.15	-	Hann.Münden 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
JEvM001	AD1467	AD1675	5.15	\	Jeanne-Elisabeth ship 5 timbers (Guibal pers comm)
GO10HZ01	AD1428	AD1582	5.13	-	Güstrow 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
LANGRES	AD1369	AD1561	5.04	-	Langres Cathedral (Bernard pers comm)
NLI01Z01	AD1428	AD1557	5.00	-	nli01Z01 3 timbers (RING revised Daly 2007)
Z031m003	AD1440	AD1525	5.00	-	Väskinde Gotland 3 timbers (Daly 2009b)
DM200003	AD1004	AD1970	4.92	-	Weserbergland (Göttingen Uni)
DM200004	30BC	AD1960	4.84	3.04	G Weser (Göttingen Uni)
H112MM02	AD1414	AD1548	3.79	4.65	Moelln Hauptstr 4 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
00651m08low...	AD1418	AD1597	3.57	4.91	B&W1 lengthening 7 timbers (Daly 2007)
G311MZ01	AD1382	AD1771	-	4.83	Hann.Münden 10 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G3141Z01	AD1382	AD1605	-	4.93	Göttingen 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
ntwe1357	AD1357	AD1724	-	4.95	NL Twente. (D.de Vries unpubl)

Table 2. Køge ship, Denmark. Result of the correlation between two average curves from the ship's frames and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

The sample marked with dark green, x455, displays high correlation with the planks from both the original hull and from the double plank layer. This is why it is not included in the average for the green group. The distinction is not striking enough to suggest that the plank is contemporary with the later double plank layer however, and its estimated felling date fits comfortably with the dating of the original building phase.

Two samples form a very small group (highlighted in purple in table 1). These are from the two keels re-used as frames. An average of these is also made (Z226M007). It is 118 years long and covers AD 1371-1488.

Filenames	-	-	Z2261M01 planks	Z226ST01 planks	Z2261M03 double planks	
-	start	dates	AD1098	AD1216	AD1264	
-	dates	end	AD1522	AD1523	AD1537	
StJM2	AD1342	AD1514	6.55	5.47	10.60	St Jakobs Church Riga 12 timbers (Daly & Zunde unpubl)
0M040004	AD1156	AD1597	23.41	19.45	11.65	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
KL15sALC1 short	AD1366	AD1536	11.92	9.24	8.35	Klaipeda Castle 11 timbers (Puckiene pers comm)
H11EOM01	AD1260	AD1495	11.65	10.32	7.20	Bordesholmer Altar 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
00751M01	AD1113	AD1463	11.43	13.52	8.83	Vejdyb ship 14 trees (Daly 1997a)
stirlingdoorsM1	AD1270	AD1524	10.91	9.41	6.68	Stirling Castle doors 10 timber (Crone pers comm)
B019M002	AD1374	AD1574	10.26	9.71	5.71	Helsingør Kulturværft two barrels 5 timbers (Daly 2009a)
HEADSx11	AD1304	AD1521	9.85	9.26	7.77	Stirling heads baltic (Crone pers comm)
Z054m001	AD1235	AD1448	9.63	8.16	6.42	Ostsee VII planks 5 timbers (Daly 2010)
vilniusZP	AD1104	AD1530	9.54	11.43	6.54	Vilnius 29 timbers (Puckiene pers comm)
H019M001 barrel	AD1355	AD1545	9.40	7.60	5.96	Algade Aalborg 16 barrel 5 timbers (Daly 2018)
se613m01	AD1197	AD1464	9.01	8.95	5.85	Hull Blaydes Staithe 3 timbers (Sheffield Uni revised Daly 2007)
BAL3_IT_AD ...	AD1307	AD1633	8.94	10.53	7.33	Baltic 3 67 timbers (Tyers & Daly unpubl)
Z1812M03	AD1410	AD1578	8.87	9.15	8.51	Kirkestræde 6 Aalborg 3 timbers (Daly & Nielsen 2016)
PM670108	AD725	AD1985	8.71	4.56	3.07	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
PERTHM6	AD1225	AD1499	8.61	7.44	6.33	Perth Museum panels baltic (Crone pers comm)
Memel Klaipeda	AD1288	AD1580	8.40	6.52	6.51	Memel Klaipėda (Brazauskas 2006)
B0352M02	AD1386	AD1489	8.39	7.89	7.41	Roskilde Stændertorvet tøndestaver 3 timbers (Daly 2015)
HMC_T165	AD1078	AD1369	8.20	7.65	4.05	Hull boards from 37 coffins Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm)
1HA00M01	AD1450	AD1590	7.98	6.85	7.16	Haarlem Wilsonplein barrel 3 timbers (van Dalen pers comm)
KlaipedaKL	AD1266	AD1536	7.87	6.92	5.69	Klaipeda 17 timbers (Puckiene pers comm)
Z084M002	AD1152	AD1438	7.78	8.95	6.56	Skaftø wreck barrel 11 timbers (Daly 2013)
Z005M002	AD1177	AD1356	7.54	3.64	-	Bølevraget Norge four beams 4 timbers (Daly & Nymoen 2008)
0680001S	AD1121	AD1398	7.54	-	-	Gdansk St Nikolaus (Wazny pers comm)
P0011009	AD1103	AD1403	7.48	4.98	-	Copper Ship wainscots (Wazny pers comm)
PP106M01	AD1110	AD1399	7.23	4.71	3.05	PL Gdansk Parc.6 14 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
Z0923M04 baltic	AD1354	AD1597	7.16	7.89	4.23	Vasa group 4 baltic 13 timbers (Daly forthcoming)
P671001M	AD980	AD1347	7.16	3.93	-	PL Elblag (Wazny pers comm)
PP125M01	AD917	AD1400	6.93	5.44	4.01	PL Elblag 150 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
0045M002	AD1109	AD1370	6.84	4.00	-	Vejby skib 18 timbers (Bonde & Jensen 1995)
0M040005	AD1257	AD1615	6.57	6.80	4.40	Baltic 2 40 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
H025M002 pl	AD1155	AD1596	6.54	5.74	4.36	Vingårdsgade Ålborg pl 5 timbers (Daly 2019)
0704002s	AD1151	AD1363	6.43	3.05	-	Poland Jeziernik (Wazny pers comm)
cesis_c4	AD1398	AD1536	6.26	4.04	6.53	Cesis Castle Cesu pilseta Latvia (Zunde pers comm)
02071M01	AD1126	AD1414	6.25	6.47	3.99	Dokøen Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
60132M02	AD1145	AD1368	6.21	4.22	-	boringholm barrels 2 lids & 3 staves (Daly 2005)
BATM001_B3 ...	AD1342	AD1609	6.18	6.96	3.25	Batavia Western Australia Baltic 3 group 10 timbers (Daly & Domínguez Delmás 2017)
E037M001	AD1401	AD1473	6.16	6.37	6.14	Påhøj Nybøl 3 timbers (Daly 2019)
0628002m	AD1225	AD1445	5.89	6.27	-	Poland Torun (Wazny pers comm)
00655M02	AD1368	AD1611	5.78	5.76	4.10	B&W Grund Skib 5. 3 trees (Daly 1997b)
P815001m	AD1262	AD1503	5.72	5.66	3.19	Poland Bielsk (Wazny pers comm)

Table 3. Køge ship, Denmark. Result of the correlation between the three average curves from the ship's planks and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

In table 2, the correlation between the two average curves from the frames and a selection of chronologies for oak in Northern Europe is shown. The large frame group (Z2261M02) is dating with tree-ring datasets from around the Low Countries, South Netherlands and Northeast France. The highest correlation is with a chronology for Westfalen. The timbers for the frames of the Køge ship seem to have grown somewhere in this region.

The average of the two reused keels is dating with some of the same tree-ring datasets, but the match is not as strong as the main group. This is not unusual for trees that probably grew in a quite open landscape, with little competition from neighbouring trees.

The correlation between the three plank groups and a range of Northern European tree-ring datasets is shown in table 3. All three groups achieve very high correlation with tree-ring datasets from the eastern Baltic region. The planks match well with a series of chronologies that are built from dendrochronological analysis of artworks. This dataset has been labelled 'Baltic 1' and 'Baltic 3' because while we know that the oaks from artworks form clear groups, and originally grew somewhere in the Baltic region, we do not as yet know where in the wider Baltic region the timber was harvested. However, the Køge ship planks are also showing highly significant correlation with datasets from the eastern Baltic region, namely with Klaipeda and Vilnius and with data from Riga.

We know that over several centuries, timber transport from the Baltic regions, for example from Gdansk, Königsberg and Riga, took place, and this transport most often took the form of planks, boards etc., rather than bulky logs. The Køge ship most probably is an example of this. The ship was most likely built in the Low Countries, for example the Netherlands or Belgium, with large curved timbers for the frames attained from the wider hinterland of the Low Countries and with planking imported from one of the Baltic ports. In this context the homogeneity of the planks is striking. It suggests that the shipment of oak for planking derived from a specific purchase of planks, rather than a stockpiling of timber at source for re-distribution.

The placement of the different groups in the structure of the ship is illustrated in fig. 5. Here the distribution of the plank groups are divided further to distinguish between the radial and tangential converted planks.

A number of samples, while dated, have not been assigned to any of the groups identified in the Køge ship timbers. While they achieve *t*-values and visual agreement with a range of chronologies, these values are not high enough to allow determination of their origin.

Fig. 5. Køge ship, Denmark. Plan of the ship (after Jeppe Færch-Jensen pers comm) highlighting the timbers from the different groups that are identified in the dendrochronological analysis. Light-green: radial planks main group, dark-green: tangential planks main group, rose-pink: radial planks same tree, dark-pink: tangential planks same tree, purple: re-used keels, orange: frames main group, blue: later riders. (note: the double planking layer is not depicted.)

Context	object	Genus
x22 p336	wedge	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
	wedge	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x27 d22	square block dunnage?	<i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine
x67 d21	plank	<i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine c. 27 rings
x190 p367	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x176 p337	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x204 p366	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x212 p365	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x229 p353	pin	<i>Salix sp./populus sp.</i> , willow/poplar
x235 p391	peg	<i>Salix sp./populus sp.</i> , willow/poplar
x237 p364	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
	peg	<i>Salix sp./populus sp.</i> , willow/poplar
x264 p342	pin	<i>Salix sp./populus sp.</i> , willow/poplar
x316 p369	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x328 p370	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x329 p338 (from x195)	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x329 p339 (from x195)	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x330 p368	trenail	<i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak
x396 d20	plank	<i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine c. 30-40 rings
x447 d19	plank	<i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine c. 40 rings

Table 4. Køge ship, Denmark. Result of the wood-anatomical examination of diverse small wood parts from the wreck.

Wood identification

Several samples were examined to determine their wood genus. Among these are trenails, wedges and pegs used for fastening planks to each other or to the frames (see list table 4). Oak dominates, as the choice of wood for these parts. A few small pegs are of willow or poplar (these two genera can seldom be differentiated through examination of the wood anatomy).

Timber availability

We see, in this study, a clear difference between the ages of the oaks for the bulk framing timbers from the Westfalen area in comparison to the planking from the south/east Baltic. In fig. 6 a plot of the growth rate of trees of the dated samples (expressed in average ring width) against the number of rings in each sample, coloured according to structural grouping, is shown. The average age of the trees used for the frames is 116 years. That of the planks of the building phase is 232 years, while the double planks were made from trees that had grown for at least 200 years. As can be seen from the diagram, one of those oaks from the South/east Baltic had grown for over 400 years.

Some selection of suitable samples for dendrochronology took place, particularly of the frames. Many frame timbers were not sampled, because they had wide rings and thus were made from younger trees. This would reinforce the suggestion that the hinterland in the Low Countries did not have tall straight trees suitable for planking, and ship-building in the region was reliant on the availability, through trade with the Baltic region, for this resource.

Fig. 6. Køge ship, Denmark. Plot of the growth rate of trees of the dated samples (expressed in average ring width) against the number of rings in each sample, coloured according to structural grouping

Method

To estimate the felling date of the trees used to make the ship two sapwood statistics have been used. For the frames that are probably from the Westfalia region in the Low Countries, a statistic for Northern Germany is used (Hollstein

1980). Oaks of c. 100 year in age here have, on average, 15-30 sapwood rings. For the planks, that are all from the south or east Baltic, a sapwood statistic for Northern Poland (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)) is used. For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the *t*-value ('*t*-test'), 'DENDRO' (Tyers, 1997) and 'CROS' (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis, the tree-ring data is compared with extensive master and site chronologies for Northern Europe.

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Con- version	extra end	Ave. ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Z226001a	Køge Skib KNV00804-1 D1 x159 frame	107	AD1389	AD1495	G	0	N	?	H1	0,93	after AD 1511
Z226002a	Køge Skib KNV00804 D2 plank løsfund	209	AD1305	AD1513	G	3	N	R	S1	0,82	AD 1519-33
Z226003a	Køge Skib KNV00804-1 D3 x117 frame	94	AD1393	AD1486	F	0	N	?	H1	0,86	after AD 1502
Z226004a	Køge Skib KNV00804-1 D4 x218 hull plank	84	AD1357	AD1440	G	0	N	R	H1	1,62	after AD 1450
Z226005b	Køge Skib KNV00804 D5 x136 frame	41			G	0	N	?	H1	1,28	undated
Z226006a	Køge ship KNV804-2 x261 d16 hull plank	171	AD1344	AD1514	G	10	N	R	S1	1,72	AD 1515-27
Z226007a	Køge ship KNV804 x132 D79 frame	75			C	14	½S/S	S	N	1,76	undated
Z2260089	Køge ship KNV804 x157 D56 frame	82	AD1443	AD1524	C	29	?	S	S1	1,69	AD 1525?
Z226009a	Køge ship KNV804 x6 D83 rider	76	AD1463	AD1538	C	20	W	S	N	1,70	AD 1538-39 winter
Z226010a	Køge ship KNV804 x368 D84 keel	55			C	13	?	O	S1	3,43	undated
Z226011a	Køge ship KNV804 x115 D69 frame	125	AD1398	AD1522	C	28	?	W	S1	0,79	AD 1523?
Z2260129	Køge ship KNV804 x311 D78 frame	143	AD1382	AD1524	C	20	½S/S	S	N	1,34	AD 1525 spring/summer
Z226013a	Køge ship KNV804 x166 D76 frame/rider	79	AD1468	AD1546	C	24	W	O	N	1,79	AD 1546-47 winter
Z2260149	Køge ship KNV804 x162 D80 frame	84	AD1441	AD1524	C	14	½S/S	O	N	3,12	AD 1525 spring/summer
Z2260159	Køge ship KNV804 x122 D70 frame	84	AD1418	AD1501	V	0	N	O	H1	1,61	after AD 1517
Z226016a	Køge ship KNV804 x309 D63 stem	141	AD1383	AD1523	C	17	½S/S	O	N	1,44	AD 1524 spring/summer
Z2260179	Køge ship KNV804 x131 D50 frame	149	AD1378	AD1526	C	36	W	O	N	0,81	AD 1526-27 winter
Z226018a	Køge ship KNV804 x142 D49 frame	56			C	10	½S/S	O	N	2,50	undated
Z226019a	Køge ship KNV804 x154 D60 frame (reused keel)	97	AD1392	AD1488	F	2	N	O	S2	2,79	AD 1496-1526
Z226020a	Køge ship KNV804 x352 D64 frame	75			G	0	N	O	H1	2,17	undated
Z226021a	Køge ship KNV804 x431 D68 frame	86	AD1427	AD1512	G	4	N	O	S1	1,26	AD 1523-38
Z226022a	Køge ship KNV804 x119 D77 frame	43			C	14	W	O	N	2,43	undated
Z226023a	Køge ship KNV804 x127 D73 frame	125	AD1402	AD1526	C	31	W	O	N	0,73	AD 1526-27 winter
Z226024a	Køge ship KNV804 x150 D65 frame	134	AD1388	AD1521	C	25	?	O	N	1,31	AD 1521?
Z226025a	Køge ship KNV804 x135 D66 frame	131	AD1393	AD1523	G	26	W	O	N	1,16	AD 1523-24 winter
Z226026a	Køge ship KNV804 x168 D71 frame	121	AD1402	AD1522	V	25	N	O	S1	0,81	AD 1523-7
Z2260279	Køge ship KNV804 x152 D81 frame	147	AD1379	AD1525	V	30	N	O	N	0,95	AD 1525
Z226028a	Køge ship KNV804 x169 D72 frame	103	AD1407	AD1509	V	15	N	O	S1	0,95	AD 1510-24
Z226029a	Køge ship KNV804 x8 D74 rider	67	AD1448	AD1514	G	0	N	O	H1	1,21	after AD 1524
Z226030a	Køge ship KNV804 x172 D61 frame fragment	50	AD1479	AD1528	C	12	W	O	N	2,45	AD 1528-29 winter
Z226031a	Køge ship KNV804 x156 D54 frame	137	AD1390	AD1526	C	29	?	O	N	1,21	AD 1526?
Z226032a	Køge ship KNV804 x267 D46 plank	262	AD1244	AD1505	G	0	N	R	H1	1,17	after AD 1515
Z2260331	Køge ship KNV804 x338 D48 plank	236	AD1266	AD1501	G	2	N	T	S1	1,12	AD 1508-20
Z2260341	Køge ship KNV804 x308 D45 ceiling	56			V	8	N	T	S1	4,85	undated
Z226035a	Køge ship KNV804 x153 D82 frame (reused keel)	103	AD1371	AD1473	G	0	N	Q	H1	2,38	after AD 1489
Z226036a	Køge ship KNV804 x159 D55 frame	153	AD1374	AD1526	V	27	W	H	N	1,20	AD 1526-27 winter
Z226037a	Køge ship KNV804 x136 D57 frame	128	AD1398	AD1525	F	30	½S/S	Q	N	1,18	AD 1526 spring/summer
Z226038a	Køge ship KNV804 x386 D67 frame	103	AD1395	AD1497	V	7	N	O	S1	1,07	AD 1505-20
Z2260399	Køge ship KNV804 x413 D75 frame	132	AD1391	AD1522	V	31	N	W	S1	0,73	AD 1523-5
Z226040a	Køge ship KNV804 x117 D62 frame	136	AD1390	AD1525	V	25	½S/S	W	N	0,83	AD 1526 spring/summer
Z226041a	Køge ship KNV804 x167 D59 frame	124	AD1389	AD1512	V	10	N	O	S1	1,38	AD 1517-32
Z226042a	Køge ship KNV804 x164 D53 frame	129	AD1391	AD1519	G	19	N	O	S1	1,50	AD 1520-30
Z226043a	Køge ship KNV804 x315 D47 double clinker plank	251	AD1287	AD1537	G	13	N	R	S1	1,04	AD 1538-47
Z226044a	Køge ship KNV804 x133 D52 frame	140	AD1387	AD1526	F	27	W	O	N	1,20	AD 1526-27 winter
Z226045a	Køge ship KNV804 x10 D51 rider	86	AD1453	AD1538	C	20	½S/S	O	N	1,45	AD 1539 spring/summer
Z226046a	Køge ship KNV804 x116 D58 frame	120	AD1405	AD1524	V	29	N	H	N	0,78	AD 1524-5
Z226047a	Køge ship KNV804 x275 D14 plank	279	AD1244	AD1522	G	16	?	T	S1	1,11	AD 1523?
Z226048a	Køge ship KNV804 x280 D10 plank	203	AD1321	AD1523	G	14	?	R	S1	1,43	AD 1524?
Z226049a	Køge ship KNV804 x184 D27 plank	310	AD1212	AD1521	G	14	N	T	S1	0,93	AD 1522-30
Z226050a	Køge ship KNV804 x185 D35 plank	271	AD1198	AD1468	G	0	N	T	N	1,14	after AD 1477
Z226051a	Køge ship KNV804 x225 D26 plank	187	AD1327	AD1513	F	0	N	T	N	1,57	after AD 1522
Z226052a	Køge ship KNV804 x260 D36 plank	177	AD1329	AD1505	G	0	N	T	N	1,85	after AD 1514
Z226053a	Køge ship KNV804 x329 D28 double plank	234	AD1302	AD1535	G	13	N	R	S1	1,05	AD 1536-45
Z226054a	Køge ship KNV804 x195 D33 plank	203	AD1308	AD1510	F	0	N	T	H1	1,40	after AD 1520
Z226055a	Køge ship KNV804 x328 D29 double plank	188	AD1348	AD1535	G	6	N	T	S1	1,28	AD 1538-52
Z226056a	Køge ship KNV804 x201 D15 plank	289	AD1226	AD1514	G	8	N	T	S1	1,05	AD 1515-29
Z226057a	Køge ship KNV804 x198 D34 plank	238	AD1280	AD1517	G	9	N	R	S1	1,27	AD 1518-31
Z226058a	Køge ship KNV804 x399 D13 plank	269	AD1241	AD1509	G	3	N	R	S1	1,15	AD 1515-29

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Con- version	extra end	Ave. ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Z226059a	Køge ship KNV804 x190 d30 plank	225	AD1290	AD1514	G	0	N	R	H1	1,37	after AD 1524
Z226060a	Køge ship KNV804 x417 d9 plank	225	AD1293	AD1517	G	11	N	R	S1	1,34	AD 1518-29
Z226061a	Køge ship KNV804 x220 d23 plank	212	AD1311	AD1522	G	5	N	R	S1	1,42	AD 1526-40
Z226062a	Køge ship KNV804 x206 d17 plank	129	AD1378	AD1506	G	2	N	R	S1	2,08	AD 1513-27
Z226063a	Køge ship KNV804 x318 d38 double plank	248	AD1264	AD1511	G	0	N	T	H1	1,01	after AD 1521
Z226064a	Køge ship KNV804 x287 d44 plank	185	AD1323	AD1507	G	0	N	T	H1	1,59	after AD 1517
Z226065a	Køge ship KNV804 x282 d39 plank	219	AD1295	AD1513	G	3	N	T	S1	1,23	AD 1519-33
Z226066a	Køge ship KNV804 x295 d41 plank	194	AD1327	AD1520	G	7	N	R	S1	1,63	AD 1522-36
Z226067a	Køge ship KNV804 x276 d40 plank	220	AD1304	AD1523	G	12	N	T	S1	1,43	AD 1524-34
Z226068a	Køge ship KNV804 x256 d43 plank	159	AD1361	AD1519	G	11	N	T	N	1,93	AD 1519-31
Z226069a	Køge ship KNV804 x320 d42 double plank	178	AD1343	AD1520	G	0	N	T	H1	1,01	after AD 1530
Z226070a	Køge ship KNV804 x322 d12 plank	197	AD1324	AD1520	G	6	N	R	S1	1,43	AD 1523-37
Z226071a	Køge ship KNV804 x210 d7 plank	407	AD1098	AD1504	G	0	N	R	H1	0,75	after AD 1514
Z226072a	Køge ship KNV804 x249 d37 plank	373	AD1150	AD1522	G	14	Y	R	N	0,86	AD 1522
Z226073a	Køge ship KNV804 x17 d25 ceiling	57			F	19	N	T	S1	4,21	undated
Z226074a	Køge ship KNV804 x327 d32 double plank	154	AD1372	AD1525	G	0	N	R	H1	1,49	after AD 1535
Z2260759	Køge ship KNV804 x455 d11 plank	234	AD1273	AD1506	G	6	N	T	S1	0,99	AD 1509-23
Z226076a	Køge ship KNV804 x214 d6 plank	269	AD1248	AD1516	G	4	N	T	S1	1,08	AD 1521-35
Z226077a	Køge ship KNV804 x178 d24 plank	242	AD1275	AD1516	G	12	N	T	S1	1,22	AD 1517-27
Z226078a	Køge ship KNV804 x187 d18 plank	253	AD1270	AD1522	G	14	N	R	N	1,22	AD 1522-31
Z226079a	Køge ship KNV804 x331 d8 plank	307	AD1216	AD1522	G	9	N	R	S1	1,02	AD 1523-36
Z226080a	Køge ship KNV804 x326 d31 double plank	149	AD1379	AD1527	G	0	N	R	H1	1,95	after AD 1537
Same tree?											
Z226ST01 planks	Køge ship KNV804-2 strong plank group same tree? QUSP	308	AD1216	AD1523						1,25	
Averages											
Z2261M01 planks	Køge ship planks 18 timbers QUSP general group green	425	AD1098	AD1522						1,11	
Z2261M02 frames	Køge wreck frames 24 timbers QUSP orange group	153	AD1374	AD1526						1,19	
Z2261M03 doubleplanks	Køge ship double planks 7 timbers QUSP blue group	274	AD1264	AD1537						1,26	
Z226M007	Køge ship KNV804 keel reused 2 timbers QUSP	118	AD1371	AD1488						2,53	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.											
Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.			29th September 2019								

When quoting these results please add the following:

in publication bibliography/literature lists:	Daly, A., 2019 Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a ship found at Køge Harbour, KNV804, Denmark. <i>dendro.dk report 2019:72</i> , Copenhagen.
In blogs and social media:	<i>dendro.dk report 2019:72</i>